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Research Article

**PARENTING STYLE, SELF-ESTEEM AND ACADEMIC
PERFORMANCE AMONG TAIBAH UNIVERSITY STUDENTS
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³Mai Alharbi**¹Assistant Professor of psychiatric nursing and mental health, ²Nursing College, Taibah University, ³ Medical College, Taibah University.**Abstract:**

It is vital to study the relationship between parenting style and self-esteem as parenting styles plays a pivotal role on development of adolescents and self-esteem is one of the main factors that affect one's good live. The current study is a cross sectional study aims to determine the relationship between Parenting Style, Self-Esteem and academic Performance among Taibah university students in Saudi Arabia Kingdom. The respondents were 200 female students from different colleges of Taibah University ages between 18 – 26 years old. Two tools were used for data collection, Parenting Style Inventory II Scale that developed by Nancy Darling (1997) was used to determine the parenting style, and Self Esteem Inventory that developed by Rosenberg(1965), was used to determine the self-esteem. The paper shows that most of the students have moderate self-esteem, the responsiveness parenting style was the most prevalent style among them followed by autonomy granting style and the demanding style was the least prevalent style. Autonomy and Responsiveness parenting styles were directly correlated with self-esteem levels while; Demandingness parenting style was inversely correlated with self-esteem levels. Students with demandingness parenting style had the highest GPA mean. The study recommends to increase the awareness about the constructive parenting styles.

Key words: self-esteem - parenting style - college student - Academic performance.**Corresponding author:****Inas Ebeid,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Adolescent's ability to go through life can be influenced by the parenting style and parent-child relationship (Kazemi et al., 2012). Parenting styles are defined as parenting behaviors and attitudes that set the emotional climate in regard to parent-child interactions (Siegler, 2011). The classifications of parenting styles are vary. To Rosenthal (2009), there are four types of parenting style authoritarian, authoritative, permissive and uninvolved. Walton (2012) stated that authoritarian parents think that their children should obey their orders without argument, in addition authoritarian parenting style has a negative effect, like the children can find it hard to deal with their anger, may develop a tendency to act out, and develop a fear of failure and often have a low self-esteem. Authoritarian parenting styles also can be indicated as demanding parenting style (Darling & Toyokawa, 1997). The authoritative or autonomy parents are characterized by high degree of kindness towards their children (Rubin & Kelly, 2015). They characterized by giving their children a chance to learn from any error they do, parents may be encouraging their children's future self-reliance (Marsiglia et al., 2007). Autonomy parenting style has a positive relation with creativity as the results of research done in Al-zahrah university-Iran, and a remarkable negative relationship between authoritarian parenting style and creativity (Mehrinejad et al., 2015). Permissive parents who put a few tying, rules or limits on their children (Okorodudu & Nwamaka, 2010). Baumrind (1996) stated that permissive or responsiveness style also is characterized by high degrees of kindness but it is a loose style in which parents put a few limitations on their children, do not encourage their children to express their emotions, and do not obligate to control the adolescents' behaviors. Parents who apply permissive style do not ask their children to be mature in behavior and promote independent behavior in their children (Hong&Long,2015). Walton (2012) stated that permissive style characterized by high responsiveness and children who live with permissive parents may tend to develop a lack of self-discipline, often become self-centered and demanding, they have a tendency to clash with authority. There is no specific definition of self-esteem. Rosenberg (1989) defined self-esteem as understood as a global evaluation of oneself. Individuals with high level of self-esteem are considered as someone who has high reliance with himself and ability to solve problems (Ross et al., 2006). Ajilchi et al., (2011) mentioned the importance of high self-esteem in challenges of life. Self-esteem has a role in psychological problems and has an important role in mindfulness that exert its beneficial effects on anxiety and depression (Franck, et al.,

2016and Bajaj et al., 2016). Some studies showed that student's academic performance affected by parenting style (Abdi et al., 2015). The study found that the relations between parenting and Chinese adolescents' academic and behavioral outcomes are very weak (Liet al., 2014). About the relationship between self-esteem and parenting style, some studies found positive relationship as in a study of Hong & Long (2015), which revealed that all types of parenting styles have a remarkable relationship with self-esteem. And Zakeri & Karimpour (2011), found positive and remarkable correlations between acceptance-involvement and psychological autonomy parenting styles and self-esteem .

The significant of study:

The aim of this study is to provide better understanding of maternal parenting style as a factor affecting self-esteem among the adolescence age. Parenting styles become main focus in the early part of 21st century(Caporella, 2007). It is important to society as it plays a pivotal role on development of children and adolescents who are important to the future. Good parenting practices can positively influence their development. Many studies e.g. Guillon (2003) which provided the association between low self-steam and the presence of psychiatric disorders. Another study sets that the most basic task for individual's mental, emotional and social health, which begins in infancy and continues until one dies, it is the construction of his/her positive self-esteem (Macdonald, 1994). From this point, it was important to study the factors that influence self-esteem. The findings of this study may help to provide some guidelines for future parenting programs that are designed to act as a preventative measure against the development of low self-esteem in children and adolescence.

SUBJECTS AND METHODS:

Study Design: This cross-sectional study was conducted to enhance our knowledge about parenting styles among college students and its' relation to their self-esteem and academic performance in Saudi Arabia. **Sample and Setting:** A convenience sample of 200 female students was recruited from Taibah University in Almadinah, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The subjects for this study were recruited from different colleges as Nursing, Medical, law, Computer Engineer...etc. **Human Subject Protection:** Before starting data collection, permission to conduct the study was obtained from the nursing and medicine Colleges. All subjects accepted the written informed consent. The subjects were notified that their participation is voluntary and they could stop completing the questionnaire at any time. Also, they

were informed that their personal data is confidential, and if the results of this study is published, their personal information will be anonymous. To ensure the confidentiality of subjects' data, completed questionnaires were kept in locked file cabinet. The electronic data were protected with secured password.

Data Collection Procedure: The researcher collected the data directly from the students through structured self-report questionnaires. The students took between 18 to 25 minutes to complete the questionnaire.

Instruments: The researchers used three parts of research tool. The first part is the *Students' and their mothers' personal data* as age, college, academic GPA, mothers age and education. The second part is *Parenting Style Inventory II Scale* that developed by *Nancy Darling (1997)*. This inventory contains 15 items, divided in to three subscales (responsiveness, authoritarian, autonomy granting). The student rated how often she engage in the different parenting practices. Scores range from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree" on a 5-point scale. At the end of each section, the scores were added up and divided by the number of questions in that section. The calculated score is students' total score for that category. The highest score indicates students' parenting style. The third part is *Self Esteem Inventory*, that developed by (*Rosenberg, 1965*) this inventory contains 10 items. Scores range from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree" on a 4-point scale. To score the test, the points values of each response should be summed. A higher score indicates greater self-esteem. In this study, revealed that Score $46 \geq 50$ indicates high

self-esteem while Score $36 \geq 45$ indicates Moderate self-esteem and Score $21 \geq 35$ indicates low self-esteem. The researcher used the original English versions of the questionnaires. Before distributing the questionnaires to subjects, two experts in research reviewed the questionnaires to assess the validity of this questionnaire. Validity and reliability were done by (Darling, 1997). In addition, Pilot study was conducted to assess the ability to use the selected questionnaire in Saudi Arabia colleges. In this pilot study, a total of 10 eligible subjects were recruited from selected college. These subjects were not being included in the final data analysis to present the findings for this study. The interviewed subjects reported that the questionnaire was acceptable, clear, and easy to understand.

Data Analysis: SPSS (version 20) was used for statistical data analysis. Descriptive statistics included means and standard deviations, and frequencies were used to analyze the data. To compare the subjects' responses, correlation tests were used to examine the relations between study variables.

RESULT:

Table(1): This table shows that 65% of students have moderate self-esteem while high and low self-esteem was equal result of 17.5 % .

Self esteem	No	%
High	35	17.5
Moderate	130	65.0
Low	35	17.5

Table (2): this table shows that the main style was Responsiveness (47%) while 31% was Autonomy and 21% was Demandingness.

Parenting style	No	%
Demandingness	43	21.5
Autonomy	63	31.5
Responsiveness	94	47.0

Graph 1: explains the relationships between the different types of parenting style and the degrees of self-esteem.

Table(3): As shown in the table, 85% of the sample was in age group 18-22 Years old, also the majority (82%) of the participants were singles, 95.5% of the sample had enough economy status. 21% of the sample was from the business college. The table shows that (64.5%) of the students' GPA was 3 to 5 degree, 48% of the sample were between having no brothers and sisters to having five brothers and sisters (0-5). 79% of the participants were in ranking between being the first daughter to the fifth daughter (1-5).

Demographic data:

Socio-demographic data of Participants		No	%
Age	18-22 Years old	85.0	170
	23-26 Years old	15.0	30
Marital status	single	92	184
	married	8.0	16
Economy status	Enough	95.5	191
	not enough	4.5	9
College	Medicine	10.0	20
	dentistry	3.5	7
	nursing	14.0	28
	medical science	4.5	9
	pharmacy	10.0	20
	computer	8.5	17
	business	21.0	42
	law	7.5	15
	preparatory	15.0	30
	other	6.0	12
GPA	$1 \geq 3$	35.5	71
	$3 \geq 5$	64.5	129
Brothers and Sisters	0-5	48.0	96
	6-10	46.5	93
	11-15	5.5	11
Order	1-5	79.0	158
	6-13	21.0	42

Table(4): This table Revealed that, 52% of the participants' mothers were in the age group 41 to 50 years old, 35.5% of the participants' mothers have university learning. 68.5% of the participants' mothers were housewives. Also, the table shows that 91% of the participants' mothers were married.

Sociodemographic data of Participants' Mothers		No	%
Mothers' age	Missed	12	6.0
	32≥40 years old	54	27.0
	41≥50 years old	104	52.0
	51≥60 years old	28	14.0
	60> years old	2	1.0
Mother. Study	Missed	10	5.0
	illiterate	14	7.0
	primary	29	14.5
	intermediate	32	16.0
	secondary	44	22.0
Mother. Job	Missed	7	3.5
	working	56	28
	house wife	137	68.5
Mother. Marital. Status	Married	182	91.0
	divorce	4	2.0
	widow	14	7.0

Table(5): this table revealed that the around half of participants (51.4%) who had high self-esteem were classified in responsiveness parenting style followed by autonomy parenting style (28.6%), and the least of respondents who have high self-esteem (20.0%) were classified in demandingness parenting style. Also, around half of participants (50.8%) who had moderate self-esteem were classified in responsiveness parenting style followed by autonomy parenting style (31.5%) and the least of respondents who have high self-esteem (17.7%) were classified in demandingness parenting style. In relation to low self-esteem, 37.1% of them classified in demandingness parenting style while 28.9% of them classified in responsiveness parenting style.

Parenting style	Self-Esteem			Paired Sample correlation	
	Low Self esteem	Moderate Self esteem	High Self esteem	Correlation	Sig.
	Mean±SD	Mean±SD	Mean±SD		
Demandingness	16.94±2.67	16.51±2.98	15.74±2.86	-.12-	.085
Autonomy	16.86±3.23	18.98±3.16	19.11±4.52	.19	.007
Responsiveness	16.37±4.30	19.26±3.45	19.57±3.70	.24	.000
Total				.150	.034

Table(6): This table shows that, Autonomy and Responsiveness parenting styles were significantly direct correlated with self-esteem levels ($r=.19$ to $r=.24$), whilst, Demandingness parenting style was an inversely significantly correlated with self-esteem levels.

Parenting style	Low self esteem		Moderate selfesteem		High self esteem	
	No	%	No	%	No	%
Demandingness	13	37.1%	23	17.7%	7	20.0%
Autonomy	12	34.3%	41	31.5%	10	28.6%
Responsiveness	10	28.9%	66	50.8%	18	51.4%
Total	35	100.0%	130	100.0%	35	100.0%

Table(7): As table shows, there is a correlation between GPA and all parenting styles ranging between ($r = -.002$ - to $r = -.163$ -), also the table shows that more than one third of the sample with GPA mean (mean=2.74) have Responsiveness parenting style, followed by Autonomy parenting style with GPA mean (mean=2.75). Whilst the Demandingness parenting style was the highest GPA mean (mean=3.31) for the quarter of the sample.

Parenting style	GPA				correlation	Sig.(p value)
	Mean \pm SD	Max	No	%		
Demandingness	3.31 \pm 1.74	4.94	43	21.5%	-.002-	.983
Autonomy	2.75 \pm 2.17	5.00	63	31.5%	-.121-	.088
Responsiveness	2.74 \pm 2.05	5.00	94	47.0%	-.163-	.021
Total	2.87 \pm 2.03	5.00	200	100.0%	-.097-	.171

Table (8): the table shows that the association between Parenting style and Age was inversely correlated with correlation ranging ($r = -.017$ - to $-.040$ -).

Parenting style	Age						correlation
	18 \geq 22 years		23 \geq 26 years		Total		
	No	%	No	%	No	%	
Demandingness	37	18.5%	6	3.0%	43	21.5%	-.017-
Autonomy	51	25.5%	12	6.0%	63	31.5%	
Responsiveness	82	41.0%	12	6.0%	94	47.0%	-.020-
Total	170	85.0%	30	15.0%	200	100.0%	-.029-

Table(9) : The table appears that more than half of the participants from age group 18 to 22 years old had a moderate self-esteem, also the table shows that the age and self-esteem were significantly inversely correlated ($r = -.024$ -)

Self-esteem	Age			
	18 \geq 22		23 \geq 26	
	No	%	No	%
High	30	15.0%	5	2.5%
moderate	109	54.5%	21	10.5%
Low	31	15.5%	4	2.0%

DISCUSSION:

Our research ended up to the result of responsiveness being the main parenting style among mothers of university students followed by autonomy and Demandingness. In this regard Davidson(2012), stated that "Saudi Arabia is considered the most conservative and authoritarian Arab society". Also another study revealed that the demanding parenting style was more in Saudi Arabia than modern countries (Alsheikh et al., 2010). In addition research of Adnan et al., (2006) resulted in that parents in a society which characterized by a flexible structure tend to use autonomy style while more demanding in Saudi Arabia. Our results may be explained by results of Alsheikh(2010) which stated that, Parents use responsive style to girls in comparison with boys and the sample of our study were girls only. Also Alsheikh(2010) revealed that children in younger ages treated with demanding style while their parents apply responsive style when they get older, which correspond with our result since our sample were of adolescents. In addition the contrast between results may be due that the mentioned researcher studied the parenting style of both parents while we concentrate more on mothers whom will be more responsiveness than fathers(Dwairy et al., 2006). This study revealed that about two thirds of the sample had a moderate self-esteem while high and low self-esteem have equal percentage of 17.5, in this regard, study done at AL Riyadh, Saudi Arabia revealed more than half (58.7%) of the sample had moderate self-esteem, while more than one third (37.7) had high self-esteem, however only 3.6% had low self-esteem (Habib et al., 2015).

Our study shows that more than half of the participants from age group 18 to 22 years old had a moderate self-esteem. In this regard, a study done at Pamukkale University, Denizli, Turkey, Students between the ages of 21-23 were shown to have a high level of self-esteem (Serinkan et al., 2013).

The difference of self-esteem level between results of two studies may be due to the involvement of male participants in the Turkey study as was shown in the same study that male students have a higher level of self-esteem than female students, while our study contains female students only. Our study also shows that the age and self-esteem were significantly inverse correlated in accordance to this results, Serinkan et al., (2013) stated that self-esteem is decreased with age. In contrast to our results, a study done at Switzerland to examine the self-esteem development from age 14 to 30 years revealed that self-esteem progresses gradually with age (Erol & Orth, 2011).

Our study revealed that Autonomy and Responsiveness parenting styles were high

significantly direct correlated with self-esteem levels, whilst, Demandingness parenting style was an inversely significantly correlated with self-esteem levels. In accordance to our results, a study done in University of Shiraz, Iran among the university student revealed that the psychological autonomy parenting styles were remarkable positive predictor of the self-esteem, whereas the behavioral strictness-supervision style didn't had a remarkable predict power for the self-esteem and this corresponds with the results of our study (Zakeria & Karimpour, 2011). Also in accordance to our results, other studies resulted in that autonomy (authoritative) parenting has a direct effect on self-esteem (Hesari Hejazi, 2011 & Ajilchi et al., 2012). Also in accordance to our results Martinez and Garcia (2007), stated that Responsiveness parenting styles were high significantly direct correlated with self-esteem levels. The responsiveness parenting includes warm and accepting, make few demands on their children (Maryann Rosenthal, 2014). And these behaviors affect positively on the child independent behavior and improve self-esteem which may explain our results. In contrast to our results, study of Walton (2012), revealed that children who live with responsiveness (permissive) parents may tend to develop absence of self-control, and tend to be aggressive.

In relation to the correlation between the parenting style and the GPA, our study stated that, the Demandingness parenting style was the highest GPA mean (mean=3.31). This results is confirmed by the study of Alsheikh N et al., (2010), which revealed that Demandingness was significantly related to overall academic performance, the more demanding the parents were the better the performance of the child in school, that may be these group of style have expectations and rules on their children that translate as good academic performance. This is in contrast to the Abdi & Yasavoli (2014), which their results indicated that students whose parents had authoritative (autonomy), style had higher academic achievement. In another study by Besharata et al., (2011), Maternal authoritative style associated positively with children's academic performance, while maternal authoritarian style associated negatively with children's academic performance. A study done in Semnan University, Iran, revealed parenting styles (authoritative, permissive and autocratic) have a direct relationship with academic achievement at the average level (Abdi et al., 2013) and this correspond to what our study revealed. However, It is unclear as to what the direction of the relationship is.

CONCLUSION:

Most of the students have moderate self-esteem, the responsiveness parenting style was the most prevalent style among them followed by autonomy granting style and the demanding style was the least prevalent style. Autonomy and Responsiveness parenting styles were directly correlated with self-esteem levels while, Demandingness parenting style was inversely correlated with self-esteem levels. Students with demandingness parenting style had the highest GPA mean.

REFERENCES:

1. Ajilchi B., Borjali A., Janbozorgi M. (2011): The Impact of a Parenting Skills Training Program on Stressed Mothers and Their Children's Self-Esteem
 - a. Level, Social and Behavioral Sciences, 30:P 316 – 326 .
2. Abdi M., Yasavoli H., Yasavoli M .(2014): Assessment of Structural Model to explain Life Satisfaction and Academic Achievement Based on Parenting Styles: Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences, 182 :page 668-67
3. Alsheikh N., Parameswaran G., Elhoweris H. (2010): Parenting Style, Self-Esteem and Student Performance in the United Arab Emirates, current issues education , 13 (1)
4. Bajaj B., Gupta R., Pande N. (2016): Self-esteem mediates the relationship between mindfulness and well-being, Personality and Individual Differences ,94:P96100.
5. Besharat M. , Azizi K. , Poursharifi H . (2011) : The relationship between parenting styles and children's academic achievement in a sample of Iranian families ,Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences ,Vol (15) , Pages 1280–1283
6. Caporella D 2007. Has today's modern lifestyle influenced parenting style? Retrieved 13 march, 2016, from <http://eprints.utar.edu.my/278/1/PY-2011-0802154.pdf>
7. Darling & Toyokawa, 199, Construction and Validation of the Parenting Style Inventory II (PSI-II), retriverd 15 march, from <http://www.oberlin.edu/faculty/ndarling/lab/psiii.pdf>
8. Davidson E . (2012) : Cross Cultural Parenting Styles, prezi retrieved 13 march 2016, from <https://prezi.com/5bsosikg-ww6/cross-cultural-parenting-styles/>
9. Dwairy M. , Achoui M. King Fahd University For Petroleum And Minerals & Abouserie R. American University Cairo& Farah A. Yarmouk University Jordan ,Inaya Ghazal I. Palestinian Counseling Center, Fayad M., H K. Khan K. (2006) : Parenting Styles In Arab Societiesa First Cross-Regional Research Study , journal of cultural psychology , 182:page 668-67
10. Emily Hughes 2013, Developmental Psychology at Vanderbilt. Vanderbilt University, retrieved 13march2016,from<https://my.vanderbilt.edu/develop>
 - a. ntalpsychologyblog/page/3/ .
11. Erol RY., Orth U. 2011, Self-esteem development from age 14 to 30 years:a longitudinalstudy,retrivered 15march2016from<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/21728448> .
12. Franck E., Vanderhasselt M., Goubert L., Loeys., Temmerman M., Raedt R. (2016): The role of self-esteem instability in the development of postnatal depression: A prospective study testing a diathesis-stress account, Journal of Behavior Therapy and Experimental Psychiatry, 50:P;15–22.
13. Gzkowska M., Kuk A., Zagorska A., Skwarek. (2016) Self-esteem of physical education students:sex differences and relationships with intelligence, current issues in personality psychology, (4)1
14. Guillon MS , Crocq MA & Bailey PE 2003. The relationship between self-esteem and psychiatric disorders in adolescents, retrieved 13 march 2016 , from <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/12711400>.
15. Hong S, sang C & rahman R. (2015) : an analysis on the relationship between parenting styles and self esteem of students of a university in malaysia: a case study , Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences, 6(4)
16. Habib F. , ALFozan H., Barnawi N., Al Motairi W. (2015) : Relationship between Body Mass Index, Self-esteem and Quality of Life among Adolescent Saudi FemaleJournalof Biology, Agriculture and Healthcare ,5 (10) .
17. Hesari Z , N.K , & Hejazi, E. (2011). The mediating role of self esteem in the relationship between the authoritative parenting style and aggression. Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences, vol (30):page .1724-1730 .
18. Kazemi A, Solokian S, Ashouri E, Marofi M 2012 : The relationship between mother's parenting style and social adaptability of adolescent girls in Isfahan ,retrieved 16 march,from<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3696974/>
19. Lombardo C . 2014, Explanation of Diana Baumrind Parenting Styles , retrieved 13-3-2016, from <http://plantingseedsbook.org/explanation-of-diana-baumrind-parenting-styles/> .
20. Li H., Walker R., Armstrong D.(2014): International note: Parenting, academic achievement and problem behaviour among Chinese adolescents, Journal of Adolescence,

- 37(4): P 387–389.
21. Maryann Rosenthal 2009, The 4 Parenting Styles. The Attached Family, Retrieved 13 march2016 , from <http://theattachedfamily.com/?p=2151> .
 22. Maher S. ,Rajabimoghadam S., Tarsafi M.(2015):T he Relationship between Style and Creativity and the Predictability of creativity by Parenting Style, Social and Behavural,205(9):56-60.
 23. Macdonald. 1994 : self esteem and promotion of mental health. Oxford journal,19 (4)
 24. Martinez, I., & García, J. (2007). Impact of parenting styles on adolescents' self-esteem and internalization of values in Spain. *The Spanish Journal of Psychology*, 10(2), 338- 348.
 25. Nwamaka G., Okorodud U. (2010): Influence of parenting Styles on Adolescent Delinquency in Delta Central Senatorial District, Edo Journal of Counselling . Delta State University .
 26. Rubin M. & M. kelly B. (2015): A cross sectional of parenting style and friendship as mediators of the relation between social class and mental health in a university community, *International Journal for Equity in Health*,14:87 .
 27. Ross R , Zeller R, Srisaeng P, Yimmee S, Sawatphanit W & Somchid S 2006 : Self-esteem, parent-child interaction, emotional support, and self-perception among Thai undergraduate nursing students.pubmed.gov, retrieved 11march 2016 .
 28. Serinkan c., Avcık c., Kaymakçı k., Alacaoğlu D. (2013) : Determination of Students Self-Esteem Levels at Pamukkale University , *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* , 116 , page 4155-4158 .
 29. S. Marsiglia C., J. Walczyk J., C. Bubottz W , A. Griffith-Ross D.,(2007):Impact of Parenting Style and Locus of control on Emerging Adults Psychological success, *Educational and Human Development*,1 (1).
 30. Walton S . 2012 , Authoritarian Parenting Style .The Positive Parenting Centre, retrieved 11 march 2016, from http://www.the-positive-parenting-centre.com/authoritarian_parenting_style.html .
 31. Zakeria H., Karimpour M. (2011) : parenting styles and self esteem , *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* , 29 , Pages 758–761 .